

Disciplinary Commons in TCS

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1 Context

Queen's University Belfast (QUB) was founded in 1845. As a regional university, it teaches a wide range of subjects. It is a member of the Russell Group of universities. Computer Science sits within the School of Electronics, Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, which is located within the Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences, one of three faculties. Each year Computer Science admits approximately 400 undergraduate students across a range of programmes, and some 300 postgraduate students across a range of taught Masters programmes.

Entrance Requirements (MEng)

A-level

AAB including at least one preferred A-level (see list below) + GCSE Mathematics grade C/4

OR

AAA including at least one relevant A-level (see list below) + GCSE Mathematics grade C/4

Preferred subjects: Mathematics, Computing or Software Systems Development

Relevant subjects: Chemistry, Digital Technology, ICT, Physics, Technology and Design or Double Award Applied ICT

CSC4003 (Algorithms: Analysis and Applications)

CSC4003 is a final (4th) year 20 CATS module available on a range of Integrated Masters Programmes: Computer Science, Software Engineering, Software and Electronic Systems Engineering, Mathematics and Computer Science. Typically, there are roughly equal numbers of students from each programme; total numbers vary in the range 30-40 per year.

2 Content

CSC4003 was developed some 40 years ago as a core module of the Computer Science programme. Since then there have been ongoing, although not substantial, changes. The module builds the formal framework around big-Oh notation and employs this in the analysis of algorithms (for time and memory complexity) from a range of domains: searching (linear, binary split, B-Trees, hash tables); sorting (Insertion Sort, Quicksort, Merge Sort); string matching (KMP, Boyer-Moore); graph processing (Prim's and Dijkstra's algorithms). A final chapter discusses P, NP and NP-Complete complexity classes, including the notion of reductions and examples such as 3SAT and Vertex cover.

Module aim

To understand some of the principal algorithms used in Computer Science; to be able to analyse and design efficient algorithms to suit particular applications.

Recommended Reading

Baase and Van Gelder: Computer Algorithms – Introduction to Design and Analysis. Pearson. 3rd Ed.

Harel and Feldman. Algorithmics: The Spirit of Computing. Addison-Wesley. 3rd Ed.

Roughgarden: Algorithms Illuminated (Omnibus Edition). Soundlikeyourself Publishing, New York.

Contents of the course notes (no. of pages)

1. Motivation 6
2. Mathematical Background 17
3. Analyzing Algorithms and Problems 7
 - Worst case, average case, complexity of problems
 - Time and memory complexity
4. Classifying Functions by Growth Rate 10
 - Definitions and properties of O , Θ , Ω .
5. Searching 32
 - Linear, Binary split, Binary trees, B-Trees, Hash Tables
6. Sorting 19

- Insertion sort, Quicksort (+ version with explicit stacking to examine memory usage), Merge sort
7. Pattern Matching 17
 - Straightforward, KMP, Boyer-Moore
 8. Graph Algorithms 23
 - Graphs, Spanning Trees, Prim's Algorithm, Dijkstra's Algorithm, DFS, BFS
 9. NP-Complete Problems 13
 - P, NP, NPC. Polynomial reductions. 3SAT \propto Vertex cover.

While the content of the course has been around for a long time, its core nature makes it timeless. The material covered represents core topics of the ACM/IEEE Computer Science Curriculum.

3 Delivery

The course is delivered across 10 weeks, two sessions each of two hours per week. Lectures are recorded (School policy). Frequent (every 20 mins or so) breaks are taken, resulting in about 90 mins of recorded delivery per two-hour session. Students are welcome to ask questions/make comments, either during delivery or at the breaks (when recording is paused). Students get the notes (as pdf) in advance. An electronic whiteboard (blank pdf + tablet screen) is used, and then saved and made available online after the lecture. Much time is spent doing examples on the whiteboard.

Because of the small numbers, there are no formal 'office hours'; rather, students may contact the lecturer ad hoc for clarifications. Mostly email suffices; occasionally students will request face-to-face or Teams meetings.

The delivery style is essentially chalk-and-talk. This is appropriate given the nature of the material and the maturity of the students.

4 Assessment

- Final examination. Three hours. 4 compulsory questions. 70%.
 - Students have access to the past five years' examination papers - but not the solutions. Students are encouraged to attempt the questions and submit their answers for feedback.
- Three summative assignments each worth 10%.
- Two formative assignments.

- Each assignment has three exam-style questions (often from past examination papers).
- Sample solutions are provided for all assignments: one week after summative deadlines; two weeks after release of formative assignments.
- Each question (exam and assignment) is a pencil-and-paper exercise. Typically students are asked to analyse an algorithm to determine its worst case or average case time complexity (counting core operations). Early assignments include practice using induction to prove properties of natural numbers and of recursive data structures (typically trees).
- For summative assignments students submit scanned pdf documents online and receive detailed feedback hand-written on their submissions.
- In marking answers the following capabilities are being assessed:
 - Understanding of the question.
 - Knowledge of the appropriate technique(s) to use.
 - Ability to formulate a logical argument/construct a proof.
 - Ability to use notation correctly.
 - Precision of expression.

There are not separate marks for each of the above: the answers are evaluated holistically, but in doing so consideration is given to the above aspects of the answer.

- Feedback: sample solutions to assignment questions are presented in a class setting. In addition, each student gets detailed feedback annotated directly onto their submission.